

CELEBRITIES ENDORSEMENT AND CORPORATE PROFITABILITY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the impact of brand ambassadors on corporate profitability. The specific objective was to examine the relationship between Brand Ambassadors and company profitability. Three hypotheses were formulated to test the theoretical assumptions of the research which included: Corporate profitability does not have any significant relationship with celebrity endorsement and Brand celebrity endorsement does not have any significant effect on consumers' buying behaviour. The research adopted interpretivism philosophy in an exploratory design and the deductive approach was adopted to interpret findings of the study. AIRTEL Nigeria Calabar branch in Cross River State was used as a case study to buttress source for primary data in the study. The population of the study comprised of 20000 subscribers, management and non management staff of the company in Calabar metropolis. A sample size of 392 respondents of the target audience was drawn using the Tayo Yamane formula. Regression analysis and Z- test statistics techniques were used to ascertain the degree of relationship and extent of significance of the variables in the study. The result revealed that there is a significant relationship between celebrity endorsement and companies' profitability, secondly, it demonstrated that celebrity endorsement does have significant effect on consumers' buying behaviour. It was concluded that there is a moral justification of companies' engagement of brand ambassadors in companies marketing strategies. The researchers therefore, recommend that, companies should consolidate on other persuading marketing options rather than depending absolutely on hiring brand representatives who consequently add up to the general prices of their products.

Keywords:

Brand Ambassadors, Celebrities, Endorsement, Celebrities Endorsement, Profitability and Organization

INTRODUCTION

A standout amongst the most important unmistakable resources of an organization is its Brand image. Its brand Ambassador is 'incumbent' on promoting to appropriately deal with their values. Building a solid brand is both an art and a science, it requires critical planning, a profound long haul commitment, and innovative design and executed marketing (Biswas, Biswas, & Das, 2006). A brand Ambassador Command extraordinary consumers' loyalty, at its heart is an incredible product and services. Advertisers of fruitful 21st Century brand Ambassadors must exceed expectations at the key brand Ambassador Management process. Key brand Ambassador Management Combine the outline and usage of advertising exercises and projects to assemble, measure, and oversee mark Ambassadors to expand their esteem. The strategic brand Ambassador Management process identify and establish brand representative positioning, Planning and executing brand Ambassador advertising, measuring and translating brand Ambassador performance and increasing and sustaining brand esteems manages with brand positioning (Biswas, Biswas, & Das, 2006).

Philip and Morris (2000), account that a standout amongst the most vital and puzzling limited time apparatuses of present day marketing administration is brand Ambassador. Nobody questions that it is powerful in exhibiting information to potential purchasers. There is additionally across the board assertion that it can be convincing to some degree and can fortify purchaser's inclination for an organization's product. Lane and Kotler (2014), expressed that these potential estimations of Brand Ambassador are tried by the reality in 1988 the main 100 U'S firm utilizing brand Ambassadors expanded their publicizing spending by 6.7% over the earlier year to an

expected 32 billion. Each of the best four (4) firms surpasses \$1 billion in brand Ambassador adverts with Philip Morris representing over \$2 billion.

The term Brand Ambassador rings a bell in the ears of nearly everybody, organizations and the whole society on the loose. It is a standout amongst the most evident parts of marketing. Numerous business substances look for the consciousness of its forthcoming purchasers while considering its investment on publicizing brand Ambassador. This is because, their knowledge signifies advertising success while sales publicizing depicts their presence (Biswas, Biswas, & Das, 2006).

Brand Ambassador is a deliberate communication with target group with the expectation of getting certain outcome from its (activities). Business firms spend their cash to convey information on their products adequately and effectively (Philip and Morris, 2000).

The fundamental goals of brand Ambassadors as investigated by Boone and Kurtz cited by Philip and Morris (2000) includes: to inform, persuade and remind potential buyers of available company products. Brand Ambassadors endeavour to condition the buyer to embrace a positive view of a product by enhancing the Likelihood of customer's willingness to purchase specific products or administrations.

Statement of the Problem

The alarming rate of the use of brand Ambassador or celebrity endorsement in advertising products and services on Television, Radio, Bill boards and Media has given the researchers the urge to find out of the impact this endorsement has on sale volume and profitability of modern day organizations. It is acclaimed that for a business organization to achieve its marketing objectives, its product must readily and widely be acceptable by the target market segment or group. In the global market and in recent times firms have been struggling to win the admiration of customers through numerous advert placements. The society is perturbed by the frequent use of well-established entertainment stars expressing differing jingles aimed at sale promotions. This has left the researchers with apprehension on what could be the reason behind this captivating attempt by companies in the past four (4) decades. Upon this backdrop one begins to imagine on the significance this overhead cost impact on organization that has made it almost impossible for firms to market their brands without endorsement of renowned public stars.

Objective of the Study

The researchers sort to investigate the following specific objectives;

1. To examine the relationship between Brand Ambassadors and company profitability.
2. To examine the effect of brand celebrity endorsement on consumers buying behaviour.
3. To identify the effect of celebrity endorsement on company brands.

Research Question

1. What is the relationship between brand Ambassadors and company's profitability?
2. What are the effects of brand celebrity endorsements on consumers buying behaviour?
3. What are the effects of celebrity endorsement on company's brand?

Research Hypotheses

Below are some theoretical assertions the researchers seek to validate in the course of the study.

H₀₁: Corporate profitability does not have any significant relationship with celebrity endorsement.

H₀₂: Brand celebrity endorsement does not have any significant effect on consumers' buying behaviour.

H₀₃: Companies brands sustainability in Nigeria does not depend on celebrity endorsement.

Review of related literatures

Celebrity endorsement has turned into a predominant type of promoting across the globe. As per industry sources, around 20% of all TV ads highlight an acclaimed individual, and roughly 10% of the dollars spent on TV promoting are utilized as a part of VIP underwriting notice (Advertising Age 1987; Sharman 1985). The number and dollar estimation of celebrity contract constitute a huge and developing bit of publicizing spending budget. A few investigations have analyzed shoppers' reaction to big name support in promoting. Discoveries demonstrate that celebrities make commercial conceivable (Biswas, Hussain, & O'Donnell, 2009) and improve message review (Friedman and Friedman 1979).

Moreover, celebrities help in the acknowledgment of brand names (Choi & Rifon, 2012), make an uplifting state of mind towards the unmistakable identity for the embraced brand (Biswas, Hussain, & O'Donnell, 2009). At last, celebrity support is accepted to produce a more prominent likelihood of clients' picking the embraced mark (Choi, Lee & Kim, 2005). Along these lines, the utilization of VIP supports is a promoting technique that should upgrade the minor estimation of ad use and make mark value by methods for the "Optional relationship" of a big name with a brand (Choi, Lee & Kim, 2005). Big name supports are costly for the firm. Contingent

upon the status of the superstar, compensation could keep running into a large number of dollars for quite a while. An agreement numerous additionally incorporate a benefit sharing arrangement. Firm regularly manufacture uncommon and exorbitant publicizing efforts around big names. For instance, Coca Cola purportedly spent and 25 million of every a publicizing effort with Bill Cost by as its representative for Coke (Advertising Age 1986). So also, IBM spent and 40 million of every a promoting effort including MASH performing artists (Byrne, Whitehead & Breen, 2003). In general, the utilization of big names as representative in promotion constitute a critical interest in elusive resources by the supporting firm a venture that administration want to counterbalance with more prominent future deals income and benefits.

The monetary estimation of key promoting choices is accepting developing enthusiasm for advertising writing. Various investigations have look at the impact of vital showcasing choices, for example, item advancements, innovative work uses, ad consumption, item quality and shopper fulfilment on firm productivity (Tom, et al, 1992: Byrne, Whitehead & Breen, 2003). Since a developing number of firms are contributing dollars and fabricate mark value, a characteristic inquiry is: what are the financial comes back from the interest in his type of publicizing. Our motivation is to evaluate the productivity of the big name underwriting publicizing technique. Past examinations on the contribution of big name underwriting have given important knowledge into clients' reaction, and in addition comprehend whether the monetary returns legitimize the cost related with such a methodology (Choi & Rifon, 2012).

Estimating the general impact of promoting uses on deals is dangerous, and an immediate appraisal of the adequacy of a superstar support company's productivity might be outlandish also, on the grounds that publicizing impact gathers extra minutes, current benefits may not precisely mirror the genuine gainfulness of a given crusade (Biswas, Biswas, & Das, 2006). The trouble related with disengaging and estimating the benefit related with a given superstar support crusade drove us to utilize an elective measure. This is the normal benefit related with a VIP underwriting effort as reflected in the anomalous return of a firm. Strange returns are estimated utilizing occasion think about system. Despite the fact that an association's benefit is affected by a few factors, and disconnecting the commitment of any one variable is troublesome, the occasion contemplate system gives a methods and extraordinary chance to get to the effect of a specific procedure on an association's normal future benefits (Choi, Lee & Kim, 2005).

Conceptualization of the Concept Brand Ambassador

Farhat and Khan (2011) posited that Brand Ambassadors are individuals who appreciate open acknowledgment by a substantial offer of a specific gathering of individuals. Though qualities like engaging quality additional customary way of life or unique aptitudes are simply illustrations and particular basic attributes can't be watched, one might say that inside a comparing social gathering famous people for the most part vary from the social standard and appreciate a high level of open mindfulness. This is valid for exemplary types of superstars, similar to performing artists (e.g Meg Ryan, Pierce Brosnan, models (e.g Naomi Campbell, Gisehe Buendehen), sports competitors (e.g Anna Kournkova, Micheal Sehumacher) performers (e.g Madorm, Winfrey, Conan O' Brien) and Pop stars (e.g Madorm, David Bowie) yet in addition for more subtle gatherings like specialist (e.g Donald Trump, Bill Gate) or government officials (e.g Rudy Giuliani, Lee Kuan Vew).

Famous people show up in broad daylight in various ways. To begin with, they show up out in the open whom satisfying their calling, e.g. Pete Sampras, who plays tennis before a group of people in Wimbledon. Besides, superstars show up out in the open by going to uncommon big name occasions, e.g. the Academy honors, or world debuts of films. Also, they are available in news, design magazines, and tabloids, which give second sources data on occasions and the private life of superstar through broad communications channels (Luna & Gupta, 2001).

Besides, famous people go about as representative in publicizing to advance item and administrations (Paek (2005). Organizations much of the time utilize representative to convey their publicizing message and persuade purchasers regarding their image a broadly utilized and exceptionally famous kind of representative is the big name endorser (Tom et al 1992). As per Silvera and Austad (2004) a 'VIP endorser is a person who is known by people in general for his or her accomplishment in regions other than that of the item pursue embraced". The corrective producer Elizabeth Ardm, for instance, utilizes the on-screen character Catherine Zeta Jones to support its scent (White, Goddard & Wilbur, 2009).

The Need for Brand Ambassador

There is an administration saying that, when the item is great, you never again must be a decent advertiser. Be that as it may, the truism is soon getting to be plainly obsolete. There are numerous item class and numerous brands overflowed in the market in every classification. Subsequently traits like quality, esteem for cash alone doesn't tally. There must be a viable media to influence the item to reach towards the clients (White, Goddard & Wilbur (2009: Silvera & Austad, 2004: Spry, Pappu & Bettina, 2011). The media here can be named as the VIP who supports by a well known superstar them if will bring about better brand review and better brand mindfulness. Individuals likewise begin partner their materialistic trifle to that of the item that they expend and the VIP related with it. Henceforth from multiple points of view the organization can exploit big name support. That is the motivation behind why organizations spend millions to advance their item with the big names (Spry, Pappu & Bettina, 2011).

Role of Brand Ambassadors

With the progression of time when the Liberalization occurred in the 1990s, we saw a spate of organizations streaming into the nation with an extensive variety of item for the shopper. These organizations didn't need their item to tail in the market thus they had extremely affricative and alluring and battles. In any case, the requirement for more benefit and piece of the overall industry influenced them to spend increasingly on their promotion (White, Goddard & Wilbur, 2009: Silvera & Austad, 2004: Spry, Pappu & Bettina, 2011). There were virtual characters for a few brands (Figo for Tup), yet for some they needed to rope in commonly recognized names to interface with their shopper and that influenced the organizations to connect their arms to Bollywood for persuasive performing artists and on-screen characters (Salmon Kham for Pepsi) et cetera. Contingent upon the promotion battles that were made there were couples of envoys who work ponders for a brand however couldn't resuscitate their enchantment when it want to different brands (Spry, Pappu & Bettina, 2011).

The Purpose of Brand Ambassador

The motivation behind the brand envoy is to associate the brand he exhibits to his picture and identity, along these lines making brand validity. As per Silvera and Austad (2004), the idea of superstar mark diplomat rotates around the way that broad communications isn't as viable any longer and that the like hood of clients focusing on the message is expanded with a big name depicting the message.

The Process of Endorsement

Individuals are captivated by big names and these famous people frequently positively affect buyer sentiments and are best in managing memory of a commercial and the brand name. The brand envoy stretches out his status to the brand. In any case, the brand frequently progresses toward becoming prisoner to the big name's picture. Famous people and whiz status can eclipse the purchasers just recollecting the big name as opposed to the item or brand. These is likewise the hazard to over uncover of certain brand envoys, whose a few VIPs underwrite an excessive number of brands, causing disarray in the psyches of the buyer (Khatri, 2006).

Brand diplomat support is, indeed, an exceptional occurrence of a more broad procedure of significance exchange. I have portrayed this general procedure of importance somewhere else in some detail (Khatri (2006) and audit in just quickly here. As indicated by this model, there is an ordinary way for the development of social significance in purchaser social orders. Importance starts something inhabitant in the socially constituted world (Larson, et al (2005).

Criteria for Choosing a Brand Ambassador

The showcasing and correspondence organization distinguished 20 characteristic organizations ought to consider before picking brand diplomat for underwriting bargains. There incorporate the accompanying.

Brand envoy:-

Product coordinate the similarity between the brand representative and the item to be underwrite will impact the viability of the support through

1. The envoy's rationale in partner him or herself with the item will impact the shopper's attributions of the diplomat.
2. The customer's trait will along these lines influence their assessment of the endorser, the commercial and the brand include.

Target Audience coordinate

The brand representative is viewed as the mouth piece for the brand and can without much of a stretch change the customer's impression of the brand.

Brand envoy fame:

Brand minister positively affect both the state of mind towards the notice and the brand. Brand diplomat are generally perceived and seen to be more believable and deliver more prominent effect on assessment of brands and its buy aim. The lifecycle of a brand diplomat's ubiquity changes as customers likewise tend to coordinate the identity of the brand minister with the brand.

Brand representative believability:

This viewpoint is viewed as most vital in support bargain. The most vital measurement of validity is dependability and aptitude with respect to the item or administrations promoted. For instance, Maria Sharapova was marked as Porsche's image diplomat in 2014. This choice was made on the premise than Sharapova "Joins top execution in her game with class and power" (Larson, et al (2005).

Values:

The estimations of the brand representative exchanging to the item or administration which they underwrite, frames the pith of utilizing a brand diplomat. As per Larson, et al (2005), Beyoncé is more than an entertainer or a legend. She is a brand. Beyonce's image is solid; connects with its gathering of people sincerely and recounts a story. These three qualities are critical for a fruitful brand.

Physical engaging quality:

The physical allure of the brand minister might be identified with the mentality of the client. As a rule appealing brand diplomat ought to be more powerful them ugly representative.

Regional and Intentional factor:

Dependent on the brand and the objective markets however the brand minister ought to be picked such that can create worldwide general effect. VIPs with worldwide acknowledgment are more significant globally than broadly.

The Importance of Brand Ambassadors

A brand envoy is the name, term, outline, image, or whatever other component that recognizes and recognizes an item from those of the contenders. A buyer views a brand as a vital piece of the item with marking enhancing the item. Unskilled customers are additionally subject to marking. For instance, in numerous parts of the nation and in addition in other underdeveloped nations, Colgate is viewed as the non specific name for toothpaste not as the name (White, Goddard & Wilbur, 2009: Silvera & Austad, 2004: Spry, Pappu & Bettina, 2011).

A brand envoy is somebody who speaks to a brand emphatically. It is the obligation of the brand envoy to express the message of an organization to buyers. A brand diplomat is characterized as a known individual who utilizes their popularity to advance an utilization superstar in their benefits (McKinney, 2014). Brands are all over the place and parts of purchasers day by day lives, yet there are sure brands, for example, Coca-Cola, Nike and M.C. Donald's which have separate themselves. These brands are symbols, implanted in our way of life and awareness. Notorious brands motivate fondness and are immediately conspicuous (Biswas, Hussain, & O'Donnell,2009).

In 2014 Google led the pack over Apple in the (Millioand Brown, 2014). Google has figure out how to develop to per penny since 2013 and has an expected estimation of \$ 159 billion. Apple's image esteem (who was the pioneer for a long time consecutively until 2014) is assessed at \$140 billion. IBM (the main worldwide business – to – business mark) stay in the third position with a brand estimation of \$64 billion. This positioning technique utilizes the perspective of potential and current purchasers of a brand together with the money related information so as to compute the brand esteem. The consolidate estimation of the best 100 most increment of 49 for every penny contrast and the valuation of 2008, amid the worldwide money related emergency (Rooney 2014). As is apparent from table 2.1, the ascent of innovative organizations and their competitiveness us clear. Table 2.1 demonstrate to positioning of the best most esteemed brands as indicated by mark z top 100 most profitable Global brands (MillwondBrown, 2014).

Table 2.1: Top 100 most valuable Global brand during 2014

Rank 2014	Brand	Category	Brand value 2014 (\$m)	Brand value change	Rank 2013
1	Google	Technology	158,843	40%	2
2	Apple	Technology	147,880	-20%	1
3	IBM	Technology	107,541	-4%	3
4	Microsoft	Technology	90,185	29%	7
5	McDonalds	Fast foods	85,706	-5%	4
6	Coca-Cola	Soft drink	80,683	3%	5
7	Visa	Credit card	79,197	41%	9
8	AT&T	Telecoms	77,883	3%	6
9	Mar/boro	Tobacco	67,341	-3%	8
10	Amazon	Retail	64,255	41%	14

Source: Millward Brown, 2014.

Brands are viewed as vital issue as per Latoret (2010:88). Brands are the key vital instrument and drivers to guarantee long haul upper hand and furthermore frame the hearth of a business' upper hand by speaking to basic assets. Brand are used to support purchaser faithfulness and certainty and to increase the value of the item (Lafort), 2010:89; Lvens and valta, 2012:1062).

Building up a solid, positive brand isn't just gainful to the maker, yet additionally to the customer and retailer. These advantages are plot beneath:

The customer

1. Easier to recognize the brand
2. Communicates the element and advantages of the brand
3. Help brand assessment
4. Reduces the hazard in obtaining the brand
5. Creates intrigue and character for the brand picture

The producer

1. Helps make brand dedication
2. Creates differential preferred standpoint
3. Slows price estimating
4. Facilitates item versification

The retailer

1. Benefits from mark advertising support by the producers
2. Attract clients

Nonetheless, brands can be lessened rapidly and feeble or gravely oversaw brands can take numerous years to backtrack effectively. Andrew and Kim (2007:350) utilized the case of Hyundai engines (Koream automaker) who is as yet endeavouring to conquer the quality issues they looked in the mid 1980's, over thirty years after the fact. Severely oversaw brand could prompt significant budgetary and market misfortune, particularly as negative data could rapidly achieve an expansive number of buyers in a brief timeframe (Andrew and Kim, 2007:351). Brand unwaveringness and mark discernment will now be founded on exchange as these elements definity affect the brand esteem.

Brand dependability

Brand faithfulness is characterized as the positive emotions a customer encounters towards a brand and the expansion sense of duty regarding repurchase result of a similar brand paying little mind to contenders' activity or changes in nature (Lazarevic, 2011:48). Lazarevic (2011:48) additionally recognizes attitudinal and behavioural segments which impacts mark steadfastness. Affitudinal reliability prompts customer's sign to make

a buy at a higher sovereign paying little heed to specific obstructions to buy, though behavioural dependability is the real re-buy activity. Attitudinal steadfastness drives the greater part of the devotion conduct and will prompt reliability after some time as this segment us mental and evaluative and will at last prompt behavioural and will prompt behavioural dedication (Lazarevic, 2011:48).

Brexendorf et al. (2010:1148) contends that the sources and advancement of brand devotion is of high significance for mark administration. Building brand reliability requires interest in showcasing programs which targets streams and potential clients to eventually impact their attitude. By impacting client's outlooks it could prompt results, for example, mark mindfulness, mark affiliation, disposition and conduct towards the brand and in the end mark unwaveringness as on basic measure for mark execution.

Brands that have solid and stable passionate associations with buyers and where the view of the brand matches with the truth of utilizing the brands item are fruitful in building brand steadfastness is produced after shopper know about brand message, create impression of the brand and have certain desires thereof. It is fortified after they planned the brand's item and are happy with it to the degree that they will buy the item again and attempt other result of the brands also (Gunelius, 2014).

List of telecommunication companies in Nigeria and their number of subsidizers for 2016 since the inception of GSM mobile operation in Nigeria in 2001

The broadcast communications division has turns out to be profoundly immersed in this way, making its promoting enrolment exceedingly focused with administrators searching for approaches to get new clients and manage officially existing clients' base. Presently, accordingly are five (5) and more media transmission organizations in Nigeria, AIRTEL, MTN, Globacom, Etisalat, streams and so on as indicated by the Nigerian correspondence Commission quarterly outline of telecoms supporters June 2015-walk 2016) the province nation has a sum of 153.2 million endorsers and about lieu et al (2011).

Companies	Subscribers
Airtel	32,77,916
MTN	60,500,000
Globalcom	36,967,712
Etisalat	22,599,670
Starcomms	4,300
Others	352,402 and above

Stinting from 2014 including down to 2017, Airtel Nigeria has Endorsement numerous big names as its image and item its worry, running from film staggers music of its speculation on support was recouped by Nike. Given that the game of golf is additionally generally mainstream outside the United States, we guess that Nike would have recouped the greater part, if not all, of its underwrites speculation through golf ball deals alone. Considering the deal in the clothing and other gear that Tiger wood likewise supported as purpose of the contact understanding, we trust that tiger wood could have summoned an even Léger contract from Nike.

Why are Companies like AIRTEL using Brand Ambassador?

Essentially "mark diplomat" is a term utilized as a part of the showcasing word in reference to a man who speaks to and advances your organization a brand envoy will underwrite the item and administrations your organization and in addition epitomize your corporate personality in appearance mien, qualities, and voice

i. Ambassador's assistance increment familiarity with your image in locales you're absent in. individuals more often than not tune in to their companions exhortation over on notice .when showcasing office target diverse areas that they one not present in, proposed message don't away land. that where mark envoy come in. last your, we began extending world wide, including the Asia pacific area. Chick out this standard for an online class that one of our ministers facilitated in India.

ii, Ambassadors enable increment to movement to your site: image minister who possess a blog can enable you to build activity to your site by connecting to your website. Not exclusively does this connection help increment

sees on your website, however in the event that your image envoy blog has a high space specialist, that connection can enable you to build CEO ranking stars entertainers, and craftsman all in all from all works of life.

Stating from 2014

Mike ezuruonye one of the conspicuous Nolly wood scuffle star was marked via airtel on the sixth of January 2014, burning his contrail finished with globalcom and he declined to Renee it the underwriting was justified regardless of a multimillion despite the fact that he declined to reveal it to people in general the previous glo envoy additionally decrease remarks on what he would miss most about glo where he was mark diplomats for two years.

Airtel Brand Ambassadors 2015

As indicated by (data .com 2015) June précising, one of the Nigerians telecoms players, AIRTEL has quite recently uncovered five Nigerian engages as brand representative driving the pink is exceedingly appraised music genius 2face Idibia, who is joined by Phyno, Patoranking entertainer Akpororo and oap, Ik, Osakioduwa. This arrangement, expert accepts, is going ahead the recuperates on the current restoration of underwriting arrangements of different stars including wear Jazzy, Iyanya, Tiwa Savage, Davido. The above names of the airtel mark minister.

Theoretical Framework

This examination is based with the edge work of three speculations in particular psychological point of view hypothesis, dispersion of advancement hypothesis and the social learning hypothesis which help in revealing insight in seeing how buyers frame positive or negative assessments of VIPs and the supported item.

Cognitive perspective theory:

According to (Black Jay et al, 1995) the clinicians think about figuring out how to consider how individuals translate the occasions and jolts around them, forming of their activities as indicated by their individual understandings. These understandings, considerations, desires and recognitions are known as perceptions that are mental process. This includes choice - making and dialect. As per (Sullivan, 1953) people collaborations are emphatically influenced by the pictures a man frames in his psyche and start forming mental self portrait, recognition, reactions and conduct. Once the individual finds a match to a huge other, this will decide how the individual will react to a big name supporting an item (Baum and Andersen, 1994) According to this similarity the mind learns, process it in different ways and create yield as codes, words and practices. (Dark J. et al 1995) This hypothesis is in help of superstar support in promotion on customers in light of the fact that the more data is said or shown to gathering of people the more they are impacted and see the data is valid and appropriate for them to manage in utilization of items.

Social Learning Theory:

The social learning hypothesis likewise called observational learning happens as people learn by watching conduct of others (Tripp, Jensen & Carlson, 1994) Learning to create conduct showed by a model is called displaying; vicarious conditions mean learning by watching the outcomes of a conduct for another person. The effect of observational learning is tremendous, from figuring out how to give a discourse, how to feel and act when somebody tells a proper joke, realizing what sort of garments, hair styles, items or eating methodologies to take. Observational learning in which human or other creature figures out how to deliver conduct displayed by a model is called demonstrating. As opined by Luna & Gupta, (2001) the most surely understood displaying thinks about were finished and his partners on kids forceful conduct (1961, 1963). In these investigations kids watched a grown-up show connecting with an extensive inflatable doll named Bobo. One gathering of kids watched the model carry on in a quelled way, while different gatherings watched the model verbally and physically assault the doll, in actuality, on film.

Youngsters who watched the model acting forcefully showed about twice as much forceful as the individuals who viewed the no forceful model or no model by any stretch of the imagination. The probability that a man will impersonate a model relies upon various variables, for example, the model's distinction, amiability and allure. Regardless of whether individual really performs demonstrated conduct relies upon the conduct's conceivable result. This result hope is, itself, frequently learned through an observational learning component called vicarious moulding meaning a man takes in the outcomes for another person. This hypothesis clarifies how utilization of big name support in promotion influences or impacts gathering of people utilization goals since they watch, listen watch and would need to expend what the famous people underwrite (Zhang & Neelankavi, 1997).

Diffusion of Innovation Theory:

Diffusion of advancements hypothesis that looks to clarify how, why, and at what rate new thoughts and innovation spread through societies. The primary defender and figure of this hypothesis is Everett Rodgers in (1986). Diffusion is the procedure through which a development is imparted through specific channels over a period time among the individuals from a social framework. Tripp, Jensen & Carlson (1994) embraced that the hypothesis has four components that impact the spread of another thought: advancement, correspondence channels, time and social framework. Dissemination happens through a blend of the requirement for people to diminish individual vulnerability when given new data, requirement for people to react to their view of what particular tenable others are considering and doing and to general felt social strain to do as others have done. On the off chance that the potential adopter trusts the advancement to intrigue and with potential for profits by regarded and put stock in conclusion pioneers, there is a probability of getting impacted.

This theory is pertinent in the appropriation procedure, in which an individual or gathering people are stood up to with a development and respond to it somehow. The reception procedure is separated in four phases in particular; the information, influence, choice, execution and affirmation stages. The crowd gains thought, learning from commercial supported by VIPs about an item in the market, along these lines making the message powerful to the neighbourhood or conventional gathering of people. They at that point shape sentiments, dispositions, either positive or negative towards or about the development or a thought. Influence likewise happens through associates who as of now have some involvement with the development (Zhang & Neelankavi, 1997). The conduct is then imitated. The people decide on the development or thought they can either dismiss or acknowledge the thought or advancements. People start utilizing the advancement or items.

The study is anchored on the social learning theory on account of the fact that people learn by observations and by watching the outcomes of a conduct for another person.

METHODOLOGY

On the premise that these research topic was time and context dependent, and the researchers believed that there are variegated, but equally valid perspectives of interpreting reality and the phenomenon under consideration was subject to human behaviour, the chosen philosophy of the researchers was interpretivism. The study adopted an exploratory survey design in the course of the research. The deductive research approach was also adopted owing to the fact that the researchers were matching their assertions and findings to existing literatures and theories related to the phenomenon under discussion. Since the research was not a life project, and it was not also an action research, nor was it basically an archival research, the researchers adopted a case study strategy with a focus on AIRTEL Nigeria Calabar Branch, Cross River State. This was to keep the topic under manageable limit. The population of the study comprised of 20,000 subscribers of the network covering; both management and non management staff as well as customers of the network. A sample size of 392 subscribers was drawn from the population of study using the Taro Yamane formula comprising of the stated categories of target audience. Main while, a well structure close-ended questionnaire was adopted to collect primary data while secondary data were sourced from scholarly articles in online journal archives. In validating the hypotheses of the research, regression analysis and the Z-test statistical techniques were adopted to test the degree of association and significance of the variables in the study. Test statistics for regression is given thus;

Hypothesis One

H₀: Corporate profitability does not have any significant relationship with celebrity endorsement.

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Table 1: Johansen Co-integration Result for the series: Corporate profitability and Celebrity endorsement using Trace Statistic Unrestricted Co-integration Rank Test (Trace) Hypothesized Trace 0.05 No. of CE(s) Eigen value Statistic Critical Value Prob.**

None * 0.722699, 76.92989, 63.87610 0.0027 At most 1 * 0.646724 44.86356 42.91525 0.0315 trace test indicates 2 co integrating equation at the 0.05 level

Source: Author's Calculation 2018

() denotes rejection of the hypothesis at 5% (*significance level). L.R test indicates 6 co-integrating equation at 5% level of significance. Normalized Co-integrating Coefficients:

1 co-integrating Equation. From the table 1 above, since the trace statistics of 76.92989 is greater than 0.05 percent critical value of 63.87610 with p – value of 0.0027 which is less than 0.05, while the respective of the trace statistic are greater than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis and conclude that there is evidence of one co integrating equation. This depicts the long run relationship between corporate profitability and celebrity

endorsement in Nigeria. Similarly, the maximum Eigen value test also, reveals the presence of a long run relationship between corporate profitability and celebrity endorsement. From the table 1 above, since the Max – eign statistics are greater than 0.05 critical values, the study reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is evidence of co integrating equations. These are supported by their respectively p – value of 0.0027 which are less than 0.05. However, from the result, co- integration is said to exist since the trace statistic co-integration equation in tables 1. This implies that there is a long run relationship among the dependent variable and the independent variables.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Brand celebrity endorsement does not have any significant effect on consumers' buying behavior.

Table 2: Responses to ascertain if brand celebrity endorsement has significant effect on consumers' buying behavior

Questions	SA/A	SD/D	Total
Do you believe that brand celebrity endorsement have significant effect on consumers' buying behavior?	270	70	340
Percentage ratio	(79%)	(21%)	100

Source: Survey Data, 2017.

Table 2: Shows that;

$$P = 270 \approx 79\%$$

$$n = 340$$

$$P_0 = 0.5$$

$$\therefore Z = \frac{0.79 - 0.5}{\sqrt{0.5(1 - 0.5)/340}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.29}{\sqrt{0.25/340}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.3}{\sqrt{0.0007353}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.3}{0.027}$$

$$Z = 11.11$$

Decision: Since the computed Z (11.11) is more than its critical value (1.96) we reject H₀ and accept H₁ which states that brand celebrity endorsement have significant effect on consumers' buying behavior.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: Companies brand sustainability in Nigeria does not depend on celebrity endorsement.

Table 3: Responses to ascertain if companies brand sustainability in Nigeria depends on celebrity endorsement

Questions	SA/A	SD/D	Total
Does companies brand sustainability depends on celebrity endorsement?	255	85	340
Percentage ratio	(75%)	(25%)	100

Source: Survey Data, 2017.

Table 3: Shows that;

$$P = 255 \approx 75\%$$

$$n = 340$$

$$P_0 = 0.5$$

$$\therefore Z = \frac{0.75 - 0.5}{\sqrt{0.5(1-0.5)/340}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.25}{\sqrt{0.25/340}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.25}{\sqrt{0.0007353}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.25}{0.027}$$

$$Z = 9.26$$

Decision: Since the computed Z (9.26) is more than its critical value (1.96) we reject H_0 and accept H_1 which states that companies brand sustainability in Nigeria depends on celebrity endorsement.

DISCUSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between celebrity endorsement and company profitability. This result buttressed on the section of the research emphasizing the impact celebrities creates on companies brands, thus show casing high patronage from selected target groups which readily impact on company's profitability. Secondly, the Z-test result of hypothesis two revealed that, brand celebrities endorsement has strong significant effect on consumer buying behaviours. These suffixes to say that, consumers of company's products are often attracted to company's brands with high profile celebrities identifying themselves with the brands. Consumers are often influenced on the perception that by celebrities endorsing a product, it demonstrates users experience and the extent of the product functional ability. Lastly, results from hypothesis three statistically prove that company's brand sustainability in Nigeria and in any part of the world depends on the celebrities' consistent endorsement of the brand. Therefore for companies' products and services to be sustained in both domestic and foreign markets for a long period of time in its life cycle, it must be recognize and accepted by notable celebrities in the society as users of the brand.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

It was concluded by the researchers that brand ambassador offers something of values to stakeholders of an organization. without celebrity endorsement, the consumer will be ignorant of the developments and event in the business world while the producer or supplier will nut salt the product since nobody will know about them let alone patronizing. Therefore, it seems safe at this juncture to deduce that without celebrity endorsement businesses will not survive. Secondly, a notable deduction from this study is that celebrity endorsement cost is justified. It is justified in the sense that anything that is valuable must cost something before it is acquired. Although celebrity endorsement influences the overall prices of product, their need cannot be over-emphasize.

From the forgoing, the researchers therefore recommend the following: companies should consolidate on other persuading marketing options rather than depending absolutely on hiring brand representatives who consequently add up to the general prices of their products. Secondly, it must be certain that endorsers of companies products and services actually utilises this product and services and not merely deceiving their target audience to influence sale volume on the advantages of their contractors. Lastly, companies should look internally, by raising high profile staff and enhancing good public image of such staff that can influence consumer buying behaviours rather than hiring brand ambassadors externally. If this is done, companies will pay less, cut cost and optimise profit.

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